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QUALITY ASSURANCE FROM LABORATORY TO FIELD: NOVEL TEST SOLUTIONS FOR SOILING-PRONE PV SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT: Site-specific quality assurance, from laboratory to the field, is crucial for enhancing the performance and reliability of photovoltaic (PV) plants, especially in challenging environments with stress/loss factors like soiling, ultraviolet (UV) radiation, humidity or moisture ingress. The impact of soiling on power losses in PV installations, particularly in arid/desert areas, marine environments, and areas near mines or intense agriculture, underscores the necessity for proactive monitoring and quality control for such PV plants. Existing commercial soiling test solutions are not standalone devices while their output data (e.g. soiling ratio measurements), do not directly correlate with the overall impact of soiling on PV plant's power output. In this paper, we present the development, prototyping, validation and first field results of two innovative solutions, "E-Dust" and "SoilRatio" developed in the framework of H2020 SERENDI-PV, leaping beyond the state-of-the-art in soiling-specific PV quality control. The advanced in-field assessments of soiling provided by these two novel tools are further complemented by a lab-based setup and protocol, developed by CEA, for (controlled) soiling testing, including PV design and cleaning optimization.

Keywords: PV modules; PV systems; PV quality assurance; soiling; PV operations and maintenance; soiling losses.

1 RATIONALE and AIM

Site-specific quality assurance plays a pivotal role in improving performance and reliability of PV plants, while optimizing their O&M, particularly for installations susceptible to challenging environmental conditions and stressors such as soiling buildup, ultraviolet (UV) exposure, humidity or moisture ingress [1-3].

Soiling is an issue commonly confronted in the O&M context, especially for PV installations in certain regions and (micro)climatic profiles, i.e. prone to dust or air pollution, humidity, water/salt mists, organic matter and seasonal effects such as pollen and airborne sand. These conditions are experienced notably in arid/desert areas but also in marine/saltwater environments (e.g. floating PV) or sites in the proximity of mines or intense agricultural activity (as in the case of agrivoltaics) [4]. Return-of-experience (REX) from such soiling prone PV plants is highly suggestive of significant associated power losses, emphasizing the need for proactive – if not predictive – monitoring of soiling and quality control in the field; to be leveraged, in turn, for optimizing soiling mitigation plans. In addition, PV systems at the proximity of water surfaces can be subject to relatively more aggressive combined levels of humidity/moisture, salt mist spraying and UV radiation (due to reflectance).

In this context, advances in site-specific qualification protocols and testing solutions are in the R&D spotlight, being indispensable for establishing rigorous quality assurance and environmental stress-resilience of PV plants, from material/design (in-lab testing) level to system operations (field-testing). In the EU-funded H2020 project SERENDI-PV [5], we have been striving to address exactly such needs of the PV industry for quality control and assurance in emerging PV technologies (such as bifacial or

floating PV) and site-specific conditions.

In this paper, we present the development, prototyping, validation and (upcoming) demonstration results of two innovative solutions, beyond the state-of-the-art in soiling-specific PV quality control:

1. "E-Dust", a novel in-field soiling test kit for PV plants, developed (and soon to be commercialized) by QPV;
2. A soiling testing framework by CEA, encompassing an in-lab (controlled) soiling testing protocol and "SoilRatio", a novel setup for in-field PV soiling monitoring and evaluation, based on patented features [6].

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Concept and novelty of "E-Dust" soiling test kit

The most common methods for estimating electrical energy losses due to soiling are to use optical sensors or to compare the short-circuit current of two solar devices (clean vs dusted). These approaches may be sufficient to calculate soiling irradiance losses, but are not designed to address the real effective power losses that soiling causes in PV modules. In fact, as soiling deposition is dominated by prevailing winds, dust patterns are usually non homogeneous (Fig. 1, left and middle). This kind of dust distributions create "steps" in the I-V curve of the modules, thus affecting the maximum power point, PM, more than the ISC (which can be understood as the irradiance affection). As an example, Fig. 1 (right) presents the I-V curves of the PV modules, before and after being cleaned. Power output (P_{out}) loss is 30% higher than short-circuit current (I_{sc}) loss.

Figure 1: Left and Middle: The most usual soiling deposition in a PV plant, dominated by prevailing winds. Right: This type of soiling causes "steps" in the I-V curve of the modules (when comparing the two I-V curves before and after cleaning), increasing the soiling impact, as showing in this example case.

To address such limitation and quantify the real (effective) PV power losses due to soiling, QPV has worked on a novel soiling sensing approach, implemented today under the name "E-Dust". E-Dust is a soiling sensor based on the use of two PV modules (clean and dusted) from the same batches, installed in the same structures (PV arrays) and exposed to the same wind and tracking conditions as the rest of PV modules that make up the PV plant. Again, the full I-V curve of both modules is simultaneously and periodically measured. As a comparative measure is carried out, no specific calibration is needed, as the system automatically calibrates itself when both modules are cleaned.

2.2 Concept and novelty of "SoilRatio" soiling test kit

CEA-INES has been working, over almost a decade, on evolving a concept for autonomous in-field monitoring and precise quantification of the soiling rate, including soiling losses evaluation, in operating PV plants. As of today, most commercial soiling test kits employ two devices or "sensors", one being a (standard) PV module and the other, so-called reference, typically being either a single-cell PV module or a PV mini-module. Other commercialized concepts involve a photodiode optical sensor that has to be calibrated with the target type of soiling. These sensors are preferably mounted on the same frame, with the (pre)requisite that the reference device/module is regularly cleaned. None of the existing (commercial) soiling test kits can be considered as stand-alone device for soiling measurements and assessments in

PV plants. Besides the output data (soiling ratio measurements) generated by such solutions are not directly associated with the overall (potential) impact of soiling on the power output (i.e. soiling losses) at PV plant level; hence, requiring post-treatment and interpretation.

CEA's soiling testing concept proposes a "intervention-free" approach, i.e. a stand-alone setup of two devices/sensors, of which one is constantly kept under a protective cover, throughout the measurement intervals, thus remaining perfectly clean before each soiling measurement. This way, the sensor does not require any cleaning, which guarantees optimal accuracy, with barely any need for intervention, thus minimal operating or maintenance costs for the whole setup.

Following its proof-of-concept (PoC) and preliminary demonstration stages, an important milestone was recently reached, in the framework of SERENDI-PV project, with the manufacturing and validation of the final version of the industrial prototype, called "SoilRatio" (Fig. 2). In its hardware and firmware, the current SoilRatio prototype incorporates three features beyond the state-of-the-art:

1. Fully autonomous (i.e. stand-alone, self-powered and self-calibrated) monitoring of soiling ratio in the field;
2. Algorithm for post-treatment (analysis) of soiling data;
3. Precise qualification of the soiling type and quantification of associated power losses.

Figure 2: The development of SoilRatio, from PoC to today's prototype towards demonstration.

The SoilRatio setup integrates a customized multi-zone PV module (overview in Fig. 2, upper right; detail in Fig. 3), each zone being an independent sensor, a

configuration that allows precise qualification of the soiling type (e.g. uniform/localized). The soiling data analysis is based on the post-treatment of the multi-zone

measurements and their extrapolation to PV array, up to PV plant level. For the latter, SoilRatio's algorithm takes into account the electrical architecture of the PV installation, to then calculate the PV plant's power output losses

Figure 3: Implementation and schematic of the “multizone module” electrical architecture, employed in the current version of SoilRatio prototype.

2.2.1 Quantification of the impact of module fouling/soiling with the SoilRatio measurement kit

The methodology consists of comparing the short-circuit current of a PV module-zone exposed to the ambient (thus soiling contamination) conditions, with that of a PV module-zone that is covered inside a drawer (thus protected from soiling) for the time interval between two soiling test measurements. The protected PV module is exposed to soiling only for the minimum time necessary for a measurement. This comparison of short-circuit currents is expressed by the parameter called "Soiling Ratio" defined by the following formula:

$$SR = \frac{I_{sc_{corr_exp}}}{I_{sc_{corr_prot}}}$$

The current measurements are normalized to obtain STC (Standard Test Conditions) corrected values. The correction uses PV module temperature values measured (also within the SoilRatio kit) for each PV module-zone. The PV module-zones integrated in the protected panel are used as references. We therefore consider that the irradiance ratio is equivalent to the current ratio on each of these protected PV module-zones.

$$I_{sc_{corr_prot}} = (1 + \alpha(T_{mod_{prot}} - 25)) \times I_{sc_{stc_prot}}$$

$$I_{sc_{corr_exp}} = I_{sc_{mes_exp}} (1 + \alpha(T_{mod_{exp}} - 25)) \times \frac{I_{sc_{stc_prot}}}{I_{sc_{mes_prot}}}$$

We thus obtain the simplified formula for the calculation of the Soiling Ratio:

$$SR = \frac{I_{sc_{mes_exp}} (1 + \alpha(T_{mod_{exp}} - 25))}{I_{sc_{mes_prot}} (1 + \alpha(T_{mod_{prot}} - 25))}$$

2.2.2 Overview of the auto-calibration process

SoilRatio's self-calibration process, defined and patented by CEA research team, is based on the observation that two identical PV modules in the same environment do not generate the same short-circuit current (I_{sc}) and that, most importantly, this difference varies linearly with the angle of incidence (AOI) of the light beam. Hence an additional correction to be made to the short-circuit current of the exposed module, as follows:

$$I_{sc_{Tot_Corr_exp}} = I_{sc_{corr_exp}} - (a\theta + b) \times \frac{I_{sc_{prot}}}{100}$$

This affine function model is verified for absolute AOI values below 35°. The procedure consists in carrying out

associated to soiling. Both the multizone PV module (and its electrical configuration) concept and the self-calibration procedure are features patented by CEA.

the measurements during several hours in order to cover the widest range of angles and that during a clear-sky day (zero cloud coverage).

Three conditions (“filters”) are applied, as follows:

1. Temperature difference between exposed and protected modules < 75%.
2. Current measured on each PV module zone > 4A
3. Absolute value of the angle of incidence < 35°.

Indicatively, Table 1 shows the result of the calibration performed at INES outdoor PV testing premises (N 45.6419 E 5.8753 ; Le Bourget-du-Lac, France), on the 15th February 2023. The linear regression model is confirmed by sufficiently high correlation coefficients. The regression coefficients are low, which shows that the difference generated by the AOIs is negligible. Taking into account the “offsets” allows correcting significantly the soiling ratios between 0.3% and 2%. On that period of the year, the sun (solar altitude) is still considerably low, hence the AOI in relation to the surface of the sensors inclined at 30° is at least 28°. It is therefore strongly recommended to repeat a calibration closer to the summer solstice (i.e. between late May and late June, for the northern hemisphere), when days are longest, in order to benefit from a wider range of AOIs and therefore a better accuracy on the regression coefficients and offsets.

Table 1: Calibration results for the SoilRatio, carried out at INES premises, on the 15/02/2023.

	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3	Zone 4	Zone 5
Coef. Reg.	0.006	0.007	0.006	0.013	0.014
Offset	-1.178	-0.868	0.355	1.983	1.685
R ²	0.851	0.899	0.895	0.911	0.903
SR before	0.989	0.996	1.009	1.022	1.018
SR after	1.001	1.005	1.006	1.002	1.001

2.2.3 Improving measurement accuracy by identifying the smallest AOI

As mentioned earlier, the angle of incidence can cause a deviation in the measurement. Even if this is corrected by the calibration process, it is still preferable to minimize it as much as possible by carrying out the measurements at the time when the AOI is the lowest, for the specific location and day of the year. To identify these moments, a calculation is performed by integrating the parameters entered at the time of installation, namely Global Positioning System (GPS) coordinates, tilt, orientation and altitude. The results are shown in Fig. 4. Once calculated, the optimal opening times were made available to the SoilRatio kit which took them into account when it was set at “automatic measurement” mode on 28/02/2023.

Figure 4: Minimum incidence angle time for each day, for the period from February 2023 to February 2024.

2.3 In-lab setup for controlled soiling and cleaning tests

In parallel to SoilRatio prototype's development, we have also designed a complete in-lab protocol for controlled replication of soiling and cleaning tests, for different bill of materials (BOM) of PV modules, as well as soiling type characterization/analysis.

Two specific test benches developed and operating at CEA are employed in the designed protocol (Fig. 5): a soiling chamber (Fig. 5, up) and a cleaning chamber (Fig. 5, down). For all designed tests, the impact of soiling is quantified by means of electrical (I-V) characterization measurements of the studied PV modules/laminates, at STC, carried out in a Class A+A+A+ PASAN solar simulator.

Figure 5: The lab setup at CEA-INES developed and employed for controlled replication of soiling, cleaning tests and dust characterization. Up: the soiling chamber and its different components. Down: External and inside view of the cleaning chamber.

The soiling chamber, with its dust generator, allows to carry out a homogeneous and repeatable soiling of the modules. A precise mass of dust previously dehydrated is placed in one piston. This piston is part of the dust generator, which allows a good control of the injected dust volume flow. Carried by dry air under controlled pressure, this dust arrives on a deflector thus generating a dust cloud inside the chamber. The suspended dust will then settle on the modules installed on the sample holder plate, which can also be tilted between 0° and 90°. As such, a complete

and controlled soiling operation (or "injection") is concluded. Different devices, also components of the soiling chamber, allow adjusting key parameters, such as the temperature and the humidity for each test. Specifically, the interior temperature can be adjusted between 15°C and 50°C, that of the sample holder plate between 10°C and 50°C, while relative humidity can be set up to 90%.

The studied samples, also fabricated at CEA-INES facilities, comprise of "mini PV modules" (i.e. single-cell PV laminates), using solar cells of silicon heterojunction (SHJ) technology, in different bill of materials (BOM) combinations, i.e. different layouts of front cover coatings and encapsulants. More details on the tested scenarios are given in the results, Section 3.3. Indicatively, Fig. 6 shows one of the tested single-cell PV laminates, before (clean state) and after a soiling injection (soiled state).

The dust (soiling) type and sample used for the study originates from actual soiling collected in the field, in April 2023, in a utility-scale PV plant site located in southern France. This site has been identified by CNR (SERENDI-PV partner and PV plant owner) as susceptible to soiling due to its proximity to a quarry as well as to significant agricultural activity, both generating potentially important levels of soiling, in a region with generally little rainfall ("hot dry-summer" climate, classified as *Csa*, per the Köppen climate classification). A total 12 kg of dust/soiling was collected and sieved with a 1.6mm mesh, to be then used for the experiment.

Figure 6: Example of one the studied PV laminates-samples, before and after being subjected to a soiling injection cycle.

We have adjusted parameters taking into account the onsite real conditions and the limits of the artificial soiling equipment:

- **Scenario 1:** the deposit of dust occurs when the panel is wet due to high relative humidity (RH>70%) and because the panel is cooled (Panel T° below 17°C and chamber T° above 22°C).
- **Scenario 2:** the deposit occurs when the PV module and chamber are at 30 °C and humidity is below 30%.

The entire experimental sequence applied in this study comprises four main steps:

1. Measurement (I_{sc} and P_{max}) of a clean PV laminate-sample, which serves as reference,
2. Soiling injection,
3. Measurement,
4. Cleaning by hand; return to a completely clean module.

Through the designed testing protocol, overall aim of the specific study was to assess the impact of: i) different materials selection (BOMs) and ii) different tilt angles during injection, on their proneness of PV modules to soiling buildup (and therefore soiling losses).

3 FIRST RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Figure 7 shows the installation of an early E-Dust prototype in a PV plant, together with the clean and dirty PV modules to which it is connected.

Figure 7 : (a) The installed E-Dust prototype, (b) the PV array with a cleaned and dirty modules to which E-Dust is connected.

Figure 8 shows the evolution of the clean and dirty modules' power along a day, as measured by two E-Dust prototypes installed in the corresponding PV plants in Portugal and Mexico. Beyond the performance anomalies (as the tracking deviation observed in Figure 8-top) significant differences in the soiling ratio are observed among different hours of the day (thus, among different incidence angles). A key conclusion in this area is the evolution of power losses due to soiling over the course of the day. Several analyses have shown that hourly losses increase at lower incidence angles, therefore, this effect is more pronounced at the beginning and end of the day. As Figure 8-bottom shows, during the first two hours of the day as irradiance increases losses also increase, reaching maximum values well over 10%. At the point of most direct impact, losses are at their minimum. Once more in the evening, the losses escalate. These results make the case for continuous measurements, in order to obtain a more accurate soiling loss estimation.

Figure 8 : Day-long evolution of clean/dirty modules' power and soiling ratio as measured by E-Dust prototypes installed in Portugal (top) and Mexico (bottom).

Furthermore, Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 present the daily evolution of the soiling ratio and the energy losses due to soiling as measured by two E-Dust prototypes installed in two PV plants in Portugal and Chile, respectively. Together with the soiling ratio, real energy losses are calculated based on the PV plant production. Expected interannual effects can be observed, as the impact of the rainy season in the cleanliness of the PV modules (Portugal), together with other more local effects, as the self-cleaning effect of the windy season (Atacama desert, Chile). The obtention of

this information paves the way to optimize the cleaning campaigns (frequency, cleaning method, etc) and, therefore, the final performance of the PV plant. For example, it does not make sense to clean the PV modules at the end of the summer (Portugal case) given the cleaning effect of the rainy season coming right afterwards. Instead of that, accomplishing a cleaning campaign early August would have reduced the overall energy losses due to soiling by between 20% and 30%.

Figure 9 : Daily evolution of soiling ratio and soiling losses as measured by an E-Dust prototype installed in a Mediterranean area (Portugal).

Figure 10 : Daily evolution of soiling ratio and soiling losses as measured by an E-Dust prototypes installed in the Atacama desert (Chile).

3.2 SoilRatio validation / test campaign

A preliminary validation/test campaign of SoilRatio’s post-treatment functionalities (especially regarding the post-treatment and soiling loss calculation) has been carried out in the Q4 of 2023 at the outdoor test PV facilities of INES campus (Le Bourget-du-Lac, France). For the calculation of daily soiling ratios, the developed algorithm uses three different parameters/formulas: i) the average of the measured current ratios, ii) the median of the measured current ratios and iii) the linear regression coefficient. In order to facilitate the soiling type diagnosis, the algorithm have been developed so as to treat multiple indicators e.g. all measurement points of I_{sc} , temperature, etc. Then, similarly to the case of daily ratios, for the measurement and calculation of periodic (multiple-day) soiling ratios the developed algorithm makes use of: i) the average, ii) the median and iii) the irradiance-weighted average of daily ratios. Fig. 11 presents example (preliminary) results of the test campaign, for the period from 30/09/2023 to 03/01/2024. Figure 11 left, particularly, shows the results of the daily soiling ratio measurements per module zone and their evolution over the assessment period. Observing towards the end of the test period, SoilRatio’s zone-specific measurements are

already indicative of a moderate inhomogeneity of the soiling propagation on the test module’s surface, witnessed as slight deviations between the I_{sc} (hence the soiling ratio) in the different zones. Further characterization measurements (in-field and in-lab) are following up, in order to validate such observations regarding both the quantity and the type/quality of soiling, and the calculated soiling ratios per zone, for the exposed (uncleaned) module. Figure 11 right, presents the evolution of the (relative) power loss attributed to soiling, at PV module level, for the same tested sample (exposed, uncleaned module). In particular, we provide here a comparison between the power losses (i.e. soiling losses) calculated real-time by the built-in analysis algorithm of SoilRatio and the power losses measured by an IV tracing bench, at the same measurement intervals and the same testing period as of Figure 11, left. A first judgement of such comparison indicates that SoilRatio’s calculations present very promising accuracy, deviating in most cases by less than 0.5% in terms of relative value, from the actual measured power loss, generally showing a slight overestimation of the soiling losses. Further results and assessment on that aspect are ongoing and their presentation will follow in future work.

Figure 12: Left: daily soiling ratio calculated for all five sub-module zones of the exposed (uncleaned) PV module. Right: comparison of power losses calculated by SoilRatio vs measured by an IV tracing bench, for the same test period.

3.2 In-lab controlled soiling tests: Results

We have carried out a sequence of controlled lab-based soiling testing, characterization and loss analyses for seven different BOM scenarios applied to corresponding PV laminates/samples (Table 2), with a focus on assessing the impact of front cover type/coating and the encapsulant on soiling buildup.

Table 2: The different PV laminates-samples and BOM scenarios subjected to the indoor soiling testing protocol

Sample module	Front cover	Encapsulant	
S1	plain PV glass	TPO1 ¹	*AR: Anti-Reflection coating
S2	plain PV glass	POE ²	**AS: Anti-Soiling coating
S3	AR+AS**	TPO	***HPB: Hydrophobic
S4	AR+AS	POE	¹ TPO: Thermoplastic Polyolefin
S5	AR	TPO	² POE: Polyolefin Elastomer
S6	HPB***	TPO	
S7	White glass	TPO	

Two key metrics were defined and calculated for the study.

- The short circuit current loss rate (after soiling):

$$I_{CC_{loss}} \% = \frac{I_{CC_{dirty}} - I_{CC_{ref}}}{I_{CC_{ref}}} \times 100$$

- The short circuit gain (after cleaning):

$$I_{CC_{rel.gain}} \% = \frac{I_{CC_{cleaned}} - I_{CC_{dirty}}}{I_{CC_{ref}} - I_{CC_{dirty}}} \times 100$$

Results with regard to the BOM assessment study (Fig. 12) show that samples with white glass as front cover present the higher soiling losses, whereas anti-soiling and hydrophobic coatings seem to better “resist” against soiling buildup.

Figure 12: Comparative results on the relative current losses due to the applied soiling, for the different BOMs.

With regard to the soiling study in function of environmental conditions/scenarios (described in Section 2.3), results (Figure 13) indicate that the impact of fouling (soiling) on the I_{sc} losses is significantly higher under Scenario 1 (RH>80%, T=17°C/22°C) vs Scenario 2 (RH<30%, T=25°C/30°C) test conditions, due to dew effect favored under the former scenario, which, in turn, favors the soiling buildup.

Figure 13: Comparative results on the relative current losses due to the applied soiling, for Scenario 1 vs 2.

Further to the BOM- and environmental- specific soiling tests, we have also experimented on the impact of different tilt angles on the soiling losses. The studied tilt angles were 0°, 20°, 40°, 60°. We concentrated our tests on three sample types, i.e. white glass, AR+AS-POE and Solar-TPO, only using the dry condition injection process. This dry process generates typically fewer soiling losses, as mentioned earlier, but it is easier to control and as consequence offers excellent repeatability.

Results shown in Figure 14 indicate that soiling losses at 20° and 0° are similar, around 4.6%, whereas they are slightly lower at 40°. On the other hand, we see that the losses are more than twice lower at 60°. By extrapolating the trend curve, it is reasonable to consider that from 70° the losses would become negligible.

Figure 14: Comparative results on the impact of different tilt angles on the relative current (soiling) losses.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

We presented the development and first validation results of two novel soiling testing prototypes, addressing known limitations of commercial solutions, beyond state-of-the-art, especially with regard to the quantification and qualification of different soiling types. Both tools offer refined estimations of actual power losses, as well as (for the case of SoilRatio) calibration-free, intervention-free standalone operability. First results provide already better insights and precision in soiling measurements, especially in the case of inhomogeneous soiling, validated at test and real-scale PV sites.

In addition, the presented indoor lab-based protocol for controlled soiling tests has been proven to provide extremely valuable insights into soiling mechanisms and their interdependence with PV-, site- and environmental-specific features and conditions.

Currently both E-Dust SoilRatio are prepared to be installed and demonstrated in two utility-scale PV plants operated by SERENDI-PV partners and PV asset owners CNR and Galp. The specific PV installations, located in southern France and central-north Spain respectively, are expectedly prone to soiling buildup and (potential) losses, due to their location to an arid dusty area (for the case of Galp site) and their proximity to agricultural activities and an active quarrying site (for the case of CNR site). The demonstration period is scheduled for (at least) a full-year and will also include a benchmarking study with already installed commercial tools, along with a cleaning schedule optimization for CNR’s and Galp O&M teams, as well as a validation of soiling models developed by SERENDI-PV partners.

In the near future, we also aim to establish an extensive “soiling library” for indoor analyses, as well as to explore exploitation and commercialization routes for both tools and the indoor testing protocol.

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